

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment among Cooperative Employees

Ruby V. Catanus

Faculty, Pigcawayan National High School, Pigcawayan, Cotabato

Myrna S. Viado

Professor, University of Mindanao, Davao City

Abstract

This study determined the best fit model of organizational commitment of cooperative employees in Region XII as influenced by entrepreneurial marketing, human resource management practices and knowledge management. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and quantitative research design employing correlational technique was utilized in this study. The data were gathered from 402 cooperative employees selected through stratified random sampling and adapted questionnaires. The results of the study revealed a very high level of entrepreneurial marketing and human resource management practices while knowledge management obtained a high level. The organizational commitment obtained a very high level which means that organizational commitment are always manifested by cooperative employees. The findings of the study also revealed that human resource management practices have a significant relationship with organizational commitment but not entrepreneurial marketing and knowledge management. However, when regressed, organizational commitment was found to be influenced by the cooperatives' entrepreneurial marketing, human resource management practices and knowledge management. The best fit model on organizational commitment is Model 5. The model indicates that organizational commitment as indicated by continuance and affective is predicted by entrepreneurial marketing as indicated by resource leveraging, risk-taking orientation and proactiveness.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial marketing, human resource management practices, knowledge management, organizational commitment, Philippines*

I. INTRODUCTION

Commitment, according to Meyer, Becker and Van Dick (2006), binds a person to a target and to a course of action relevant to that target. However, the individuals should not be forced to stay in the organization (Tavallaei and Bagheri, 2012). Cooperatives play a role as a driver in economic growth and is considered a people's economic movement or a business entity that aims to prosper the community to create a just and prosperous society (Ni Nyoman, Gede & Bayu, 2019). Further, entrepreneurial marketing lies in the center of marketing and entrepreneurship and aims at making proactive utilization of opportunities through innovation. This perspective can be recognized as a successful alternative in cooperative marketing programs (Morris, Schindehutte and La Forge, 2004). Moreover, cooperatives are going through fundamental changes like other organizations. People are started to be looked as an asset in today's economic instability by the organization where he belongs. As emphasized by Robert (2006), engaged and committed employees in their work have an advantage over his competitors. Today's problem, as mentioned by Saliss and Jones (2002), is not accessing but how an organization fails to manage and utilize its knowledge. When doing so, the organization would have a slim chance of survival. How an employee judges the behavior of the organization as well the degree to which an employee experiences a sense of oneness with their organization determines the entrepreneurial level of the firm. In relation to the propositions of Nawaser, Shahmehar, Farhoudnia and Ahmadi (2015), the economic development of organizations is dependent on the role of entrepreneurship.

Nevertheless, the intensity of entrepreneurial marketing varies based on the stage of development and level of environmental turbulence faced by every organization (Morris, Schindehutte, and La Forge, 2002). In addition, human

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

resource management provide an edge to employee's commitment towards an organization goal in the global competitive market as stated in the findings of Lamba and Chouhary (2013), that the commitment and motivation built through good human resource management (HRM) practices also energize people working in the organization. In the same manner, the study of Ikechukwu (2018), knowledge management is one predictor variable that has the capacity of improving organizational commitment. Reasons being that organizational stakeholders were able to distribute knowledge among themselves, it will go a long way to solve many problems that is faced by organization. This study seeks to provide an insight into the entrepreneurial marketing, knowledge management and human resource management practices prevalent in the cooperative industry which influence organizational commitment and also pave the way for employing measures that will enhance the level of performance. On a practical level, the results of this study will hopefully provide practitioners with better insights into some practices that could be used to elevate organizational commitment.

1.1. Research Objectives

The study aimed to determine the best fit model on organizational commitment of cooperative employees in Region XII as influenced by entrepreneurial marketing, human resource management practices and knowledge management of cooperatives. Specifically, it sought to attain the following objectives: to assess the level of entrepreneurial marketing, human resource management practices, knowledge management and organizational commitment; determine the relationship between the exogenous variables and the endogenous variable; to establish the significant influence of the exogenous variables to the endogenous variable; and to identify the best fit model of organizational commitment among cooperative employees.

1.2 Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study that no significant relationship exist between entrepreneurial marketing, human resource management practices, knowledge management and organizational commitment among cooperative employees and there is no model best fits organizational commitment of cooperative employees were tested at .05 level of significance.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study is helpful to all institutions including the academe. The results of this research may significantly contribute to the understanding of the management the conditions of its employees with regards to their commitment to the organization. In particular, the results of this study may be helpful to the cooperative management to be aware, prepared and ready to the reactions of the employees with regards to the company's entrepreneurial marketing, HRM practices, knowledge management. It may also guide the management to identify the factors which affect the employees in their commitment to the cooperative and make necessary suggestions on how to improve their performances. The results of the study may be helpful particularly to the employees of the cooperatives. The results may influence them in making decisions and consider whether to stay or leave the organization. They may be able to utilize their full potential that will result to optimum organizational performance. Furthermore, globally, this study can have an impact to individuals who are devoted to management become capable of believing and accepting the organization's goals and values. Through identifying the factors that may significantly influence the employees' organizational commitment, management can now conduct researches that will in time be of value in the future.

II. METHOD

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized quantitative research design employing descriptive-correlational technique. The design is used to develop and employ mathematical models, theories and/or hypothesis pertaining to phenomena (Given, 2008). Also, the study used the Structure Equation Model (SEM) approach. This was used in determining the best fit model of organizational commitment which could be a basis for planning and intervention programs among institutions. Descriptive correlational design is concerned with how, what is, or what exists is related to some preceding event that has influence or affected a present condition or event (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2013). The approach was appropriate since the study sought to ascertain the level and determine the interrelationships between entrepreneurial marketing, HRM practices, knowledge management and organizational commitment of cooperative employees.

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

2.2 Population and Sample

Scientific process was employed in choosing the respondents. Stratified random sampling was used in determining the respondents for this study. Stratified random sampling is a widely-used method for data analysis where the population is partitioned into subgroups called "strata" (Nguyen, Tirthapura, Shih, Srivastava & Xu, 2019). Stratified random sampling provides the flexibility to emphasize some strata over others. The total completed surveys reached 402 which was way higher than the maximum number of sample in Davis (2005) computing for finite population which is 400 at .05 significance level. Respondents of the study were existing employees from 21 identified cooperatives in Region XII. Employees employed at least six months in service were considered, such that their tenure has already been established. Those newly-appointed employees were not included. For purposes of context, all cooperative employees in and outside the locale, were excluded. Likewise, workers who were no longer connected with the cooperative were excluded from the study. Participants were allowed to withdraw anytime he or she feels uncomfortable, is intimidated, or there is actual or perceived threat to physical, psychological or emotional well-being.

2.3 Research Instrument

There were four instruments in this study adapted from various sources, to wit: entrepreneurial marketing (Becherer, Hlems & McDonald, 2012), HRM practices (Jafri, 2013), knowledge management (Jain, 2014) and organizational commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1997). All the instruments were constructed based on some relevant studies and literature reviewed. Prior to the administration, the draft of these instruments were tested for face and content validity by the panel of experts in the field of business management. Based on their comments and suggestions, revisions were made. After validation, pilot testing were performed. To test for reliability, Cronbach's alpha was used (Gliem & Gliem, 2003).

2.4 Data Collection

Several procedures were performed in collecting the data used in the study. The first procedure was the acquisition of consent to administer the study. Request letter signed by the adviser and the Professional Schools dean as well as the first endorsement signed by the dean was sent to the Regional Director of Cooperative Development Authority XII for the identification of cooperatives in the region. After the receipt of the reply letter from the Regional Director, together with the list of 2019 compliant cooperatives and the second endorsement, the questionnaires were delivered to the selected cooperatives. Gradual administration and retrieval of data, collation and tabulation of data were conducted wherein a screening was done to lessen the possible outliers during the analysis. Completed survey used in this study were from 402 respondents. The remaining completed questionnaires were double checked. After which, encoding, tabulating, and analysis followed. And lastly, analysis and interpretation of data wherein results were analyzed and interpreted based on the purpose of the study.

2.5 Statistical Tool

The statistical tools utilized to analyze the data gathered in this study were mean, Pearson r, multiple regression, and Structural Equation Modeling. Mean used was to measure the level of entrepreneurial marketing, knowledge management, human resource management practices and organizational commitment; Pearson r was used to determine the interrelationships between entrepreneurial marketing, knowledge management, HRM practices and organizational commitment; multiple regression was used to determine the significant predictors of organizational commitment; and SEM was used to assess the interrelationships among the hypothesized models and to determine the best fit model of organizational commitment.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shown in table 1 is the level of entrepreneurial marketing of cooperatives. The seven indicators of entrepreneurial marketing generated an overall mean rating of 4.42 or very high. This indicates that the entrepreneurial marketing among cooperatives is very high. This also means that entrepreneurial marketing is always observed among cooperatives in Region XII. The study affirmed that entrepreneurial proactiveness is a key driving force in achieving organizational commitment: by anticipating changes or needs in the market and initiating first to act on them (Okpara, 2009; Rauch, Wiklund, Freese, & Lumpkin, 2004). Likewise, better results are achieved when entrepreneurs find new ways to create or discover value (Becherer, Finch, & Helms, 2005/6). Organizations exploit opportunities by learning and adapting innovative concepts or ideas (Morris et al., 2002). Entrepreneurs who are innovation-oriented possess innovativeness or openness to newness and display an interest to be among the first to adopt innovation (Hultman, &

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

Shaw, 2003; Marcati, Guido, & Peluso, 2008). Further, employees in the organization always takes a chance on an opportunity and is capable to use calculated actions to mitigate the risk present in every pursuit of opportunity, (Becherer et.al., 2012; Lumpkin and Dess, 2001; Morris et. al., 2002).Output of the study alludes that employees are aware that their public image may reflect consumer’s perception of their cooperative (Spence and Essoussi, 2010). Lastly people in the cooperative use internal and external resources in achieving the goals of the organization (Hamali, 2015).

TABLE 1. Entrepreneurial Marketing

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Proactiveness	0.30	4.60	Very high
Opportunity-focused	0.35	4.49	Very high
Risk-taking Orientation	0.48	4.34	Very high
Innovation-oriented	0.44	4.38	Very high
Customer Intensity	0.43	4.33	Very high
Resource Leveraging	0.41	4.23	Very high
Value Creation	0.34	4.55	Very high
Overall	0.31	4.42	Very high

InTable 2 is presented the list of the items in the four indicators of HRM practices. Thefour indicators of the HRM practices obtained an overall mean rating of 4.22 described as very high. The results showed that the human resource management practices of cooperatives is very high. This indicates that HRM practices is always observed among cooperatives in Region XII. This depicts that cooperatives develop a systematic assessment performance of their employees in his assigned tasks (Hassan, 2016). Building and developing the skills of the employees is a good investment for the organization. In addition the findings of the study assert that sorts of financial and non financial compensation are given to employees for their contribution to the organization (Jafri, 2013). Employees who are attracted to a reward system stay longer in the organization. Similarly, employees tend to stick to their cooperativebecause they are rewarded accordingly based on their performance (Kwenin, Muathe, & Nzulwa, 2013; Shoaib, Noor, Tirmizi, & Bashi, 2009; Sutherland, 2004).

TABLE 2. Human Resource Management Practices

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Training and Development	0.50	4.20	Very high
Performance Appraisal	0.47	4.21	Very high
Work Life Balance	0.52	4.22	Very high
Reward and Benefits	0.41	4.25	Very High
Overall	0.38	4.22	Very High

In Table 3 is presented the level of knowledge management. These indicators determined the knowledge management and usage of technologies among employees. The four indicators of knowledge management obtained an over-all mean of 3.92, described as high level. The level of knowledge management among cooperatives is high. This means that knowledge management is oftentimes observed among cooperatives in Region XII. Results of the study is in consonance with the research conducted on by many researchers (Chong, 2005; Civi, 2000; Moffett, McAdam, & Parkinson, 2003). They have insisted that successful knowledge management project, particularly in knowledge - creating and culture - sharing activities is dependent on top - management leadership and commitment. This also means that cooperatives are capable of managing its knowledge resources and abilities (Theriou, Maditinos & Therio,

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

2011). Moreover, cooperatives has a knowledge friendly corporate culture, management style and philosophy, among others (Albers, 2009; Becerra-Fernandez & Sabherwal, 2010; Cristina, 2009; Rehman, Mahmood, Sugathan, & Amin, 2010). Finally, results means that employees take into consideration the acquisition, processing, storage and dissemination of information by a technological based combination of computing and communications (Wei & Yeganeh, 2013).

TABLE 3. Knowledge Management

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Information Technology	0.58	3.85	High
Organizational Structure	0.64	3.88	High
Leadership and Top Management Support	0.66	4.02	High
Knowledge Management Strategy	0.78	3.93	High
Overall	0.60	3.92	High

In Table 4 is presented the list of items in the three indicators of the organizational commitment of cooperative employees in Region XII. The three indicators of organizational commitment had an overall mean rating of 4.33 or very high. The results shows that organizational commitment is always manifested by cooperative employees. This asserts that personnel stick around because of the belief that a he/she should remain loyal to the organization (Khan, Naseem & Masood, 2016). The findings also signifies that employees feel that they are part of the family at the organization and feels a strong sense of belongingness (Allen and Meyer ,1990; Delegach, Kark, Katz-Navon & Van Dijk, 2017; Nguyen and Nguyen, 2017). Lastly, employees stay in the cooperative because they need to.and feel that they should remain in the organization (Kuzehchian, Zarei & Talebpour, 2003).

TABLE 4. Organizational Commitment

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective Commitment	0.40	4.37	Very High
Normative Commitment	0.73	4.15	High
Continuance Commitment	0.50	4.48	Very high
	0.43	4.33	Very High

The data in table 5 showed the correlation between the entrepreneurial marketing and the organizational commitment of cooperative employees, the P-value that was .544 and correlation coefficient, $r = 0.030$. It can be perceived from the results that there was no significant relationship between entrepreneurial marketing and organizational commitment as reflected in the table. In addition, it can be noted that the findings of the study failed to reject the null hypothesis. On the other hand, proactiveness and value creation correlates with affective commitment. Results of the study is in consonance with the findings of Ghitulescu (2018), Parker and Wang (2015) and Wihler, Blickle, Ellen, Hochwarter, and Ferris (2017). Moreover, value creation is correlated with affective and continuance commitment. The findings also supports the studies conducted by Olsson and Matsson (2015) that value creation has a positive relationship with continuance and affective commitment. Further, the study is in consonance with the findings of Hong& Ha (2015) thatrisk-taking positively correlates with the affective commitment. The study is comparable with the findings of Becherer, et al. (2012), that all seven dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing do not relate significantly to all outcome variables of small to mid-sized enterprises. The results demonstrate that alone or in combination of these entrepreneurial marketing constructs can affect organizational commitment.

TABLE 5. Relationship between Entrepreneurial Marketing and Organizational Commitment

Entrepreneurial Marketing	Organizational Commitment			
	Affective	Normative	Continuance	Overall
Proactiveness	.130**	.011	.160**	.103*
	.009	.832	.001	.039
Opportunity-focused	.043	-.172**	.067	-.059
	.393	.001	.183	.236

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

Risk-taking Orientation	.011	-.002	.156**	.063
	.831	.970	.002	.211
Innovation-oriented	.084	-.108*	.202**	.040
	.092	.030	.000	.422
Customer Intensity	-.076	-.187**	.061	-.102*
	.129	.000	.225	.041
Resource Leveraging	.001	.022	.066	.039
	.982	.663	.186	.439
Value Creation	.103*	-.020	.178**	.086
	.039	.693	.000	.084
Overall	.044	-.081	.164**	.030
	.375	.106	.001	.544

Similarly, the data in table 6 shows the relationship between HRM practices and organizational commitment of cooperative employees was found to be significant with a P-value less than 0.05, and $r = 0.311$ which leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of the study. The overall result of HRM practices of cooperatives in Region XII is significantly correlated with the organizational commitment of employees. The result of the study is congruent with the exploration conducted by Mehwish, Abeera, Aideded & Tania (2019) on the HRM and organizational commitment. The results indicate that employees with positive perceptions about the human resources increase organizational commitment (Koc, Cavus, and Turgay, 2014; Lamba and Chouhary, 2013).

TABLE 6. Relationship between HRM Practices and Organizational Commitment

Human Resource Management Practices	Organizational Commitment			
	Affective	Normative	Continuance	Overall
Training and Development	.178**	.102*	.278**	.213**
	.000	.041	.000	.000
Performance Appraisal	.107*	.022	.277**	.149**
	.032	.664	.000	.003
Work Life Balance	.221**	.088	.384**	.258**
	.000	.076	.000	.000
Reward and Benefits	.224**	.363**	.386**	.414**
	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.224**	.166**	.406**	.311**
	.000	.001	.000	.000

In Table 7 is shown the value of correlation coefficient, $r = -.056$ and the P-value that was .262 when the level of knowledge management was correlated with the organizational commitment of employees. The results reveal that there is no significant relationship between knowledge management and the organizational commitment of employees. Hence, it can be noted that the findings of the study failed to reject the null hypothesis. The overall result of knowledge management of cooperatives in Region XII is not significantly correlated with the organizational commitment. In a singular state, the indicator information technology, is significantly correlated to organizational commitment. The results of the study is in consonance with the findings of Sadeghi & Yazdanfar (2018) that there is no meaningful relationship between the organizational commitment and knowledge management. The results contradict to the findings of the researches done by Kameli (2009) cited in Ehsan (2011), Bordbar (2014), and Ikechukwu (2018). On the other hand, the findings of the study is in consonance with the study of Sarayani, Mirineja and Keivani (2014) that there is a direct relationship between organizational commitment and information technology. According to Yeh, Lai, and Ho (2006), information technology facilitates in searching, accessing information, cooperating and communicating among organizational members.

TABLE 7. Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Commitment

Knowledge Management	Organizational Commitment			
	Affective	Normative	Continuance	Overall
Information Technology	.042	.023	.306**	.143**
	.399	.647	.000	.004
Organizational Structure	-.067	-.214**	.125*	-.090
	.183	.000	.012	.072
Leadership and Top Management Support	-.048	-.207**	.106*	-.088

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

	.341	.000	.033	.076
Knowledge Management Strategy	-.132**	-.239**	.104*	-.130**
	.008	.000	.037	.009
Overall	-.064	-.187**	.171**	-.056
	.200	.000	.001	.262

The analysis of organizational commitment as regressed on entrepreneurial marketing, HRM practices and knowledge management revealed a significant influence on organizational commitment as reflected in the F-value of 55.293 at ($p < 0.01$). The computed R² value is 0.294 which means that 29.4% of the variance of organizational commitment is due to the variance of entrepreneurial marketing, HRM practices and knowledge management. This means further that 71.6% is attributed to other variables not covered in this study. The result is significant hence the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected. The three independent variables need each other to significantly influence the dependent variable. It can be deduced that the use of entrepreneurial marketing influence the achievement of goals for the company (Becherer, et al., 2012). Moreover, perceptions held by employees that they are safe and well satisfied (Mehwish et. al., 2019), are highly influenced by their commitment to their organization and their specific personality dimension. The employees' commitment is influenced by their performance in human resource activities and the employees' awareness of their own specific roles (Nasiri, 2017). Furthermore, the propositions of Dimas and Faisal (2019) and Susanto and Putra (2019) concluded that knowledge management influences organizational commitment.

There were five generated models presented in the study. The summary of the findings of the goodness of fit measures of these five generated models is presented in Table 8. In identifying the best fit model, all indices included must consistently fall within the acceptable ranges. Chi-square/degrees of freedom value should be less than 5 with its corresponding p-value greater than 0.05. Root mean square error approximation value must be less than 0.05 and its corresponding Pclose value must be greater than 0.05. The other indices such as the normed fit index, Tucker-Lewis index, comparative fit index and the goodness of fit index must all be greater than 0.95.

TABLE 8. Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Five Generated Models

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMIN/DF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSEA (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	11.375	.716	.711	.693	.665	.161	.000
2	.000	9.471	.769	.767	.748	.726	.145	.000
3	.000	6.207	.900	.921	.908	.894	.114	.000
4	.000	6.916	.804	.838	.816	.809	.121	.000
5	.347	1.060	.998	1.000	.993	.998	.012	.637

Legend: CMIN/DF - Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom NFI - Normed Fit Index
 GFI - Goodness of Fit Index TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
 RMSEA - Root Mean Square of Error Approximation CFI - Comparative Fit Index

In terms of the research question related to the model that best represents the variables that predicts organizational commitment, the original proposed model outlined in Fig.1 requires some modification in order to fit the data. A model showing the direct causal link of the exogenous variable entrepreneurial marketing towards the organizational commitment. The model is a modified version of Model 5 wherein some indicators with low values were removed. Model 5 was found to have indices that consistently indicate a very good fit to the data as all the indices presented fall within each criterion. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no best fit model was rejected. It could be stated that there is a best fit model that predicts the organizational commitment of a cooperative employee in Region XII. The findings suggest that organizational commitment of cooperative employees was best anchored on: entrepreneurial marketing which was measured in terms of proactiveness, risk-taking orientation and resource leveraging. It could be seen from the model that only affective commitment and continuance commitment remained as the measurement construct of organizational commitment, out of the three indicators. The need to connect employees are better understood by organizations to improve/strengthen their organizational commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Delegach et al., 2017; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2017). Cooperatives exhibit proactiveness, which reveals themselves through actions in a formulation of stated belief and the implantations of these beliefs (Rosemond, Edward & Moses, 2012). In addition,

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

cooperatives are also risk-takers and capable in identifying risk factors, and mitigating or sharing those factors (Becherer et al., 2012; Morris et al., 2002). Lastly, cooperatives can leverage their resources and are capable in doing more with less as well recognize a resource not being used optimally (Morris et al., 2002).

Figure1. Direct Causal Link of the Exogenous Variable Entrepreneurial Marketing Towards the Organizational Commitment

IV. Conclusion

In the light of the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn. The very high level of entrepreneurial marketing and HRM practices and high level of knowledge management may introduce useful views and conclusion for the management to take into account for maintaining these perception among cooperative employees. Committed employees remain loyal thus allowing them to have a continuous stream of labor and retain valuable personnel will help cooperatives achieve its goal. Affective and continuance commitment may improve organizational commitment but it is better to gain the affection of employees, that they may stay not because they have to or due to the cost associated if they leave the organization but because their heart and loyalty is with the organization. Organizational commitment of cooperative employees was best anchored on entrepreneurial marketing which was measured in terms of proactiveness, risk-taking orientation and resource leveraging. The research findings of this study are only limited to cooperatives operating in the Region XII. Thus, further researches should be conducted in other regions and cooperatives in order to confirm, contradict and generalize the results. Sectoral differences should also be taken into account. Due to the varying nature of each sector or industry, applying organizational commitment concept into different sectors might generate different results compared to those in cooperative sector.

REFERENCES

- [1] Meyer, J., Becker, T., & Van Dick, R. (2006). Social Identities and Commitment at Work: Toward an Integrative Model. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 27, pp. 665-683.
- [2] Tavallaei, R.A., & Bagheri, M. (2012). *The effect of organizational commitment on organization reviewed*. Police Human Development, 7(30), 73-96.
- [3] Ni Nyoman S., Gede G., and Gde Bayu S.P. (2019). *The Effect of Organizational Compensation and Commitment to Organizational Citizenship Behavior in the Cooperative and Small, Middle Enterprises Department of Bali Province*. International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review, Vol. 10, Issue. 01, Page no: ME 21210-21218 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15520/ijcrr.v10i01.643>
- [4] Morris, M.H., Schindehutte, M., & La Forge, R.W. (2004). *The emergence of entrepreneurial marketing: nature and meaning*. Editor: Harold P. Welsch. Entrepreneurship: The Way Ahead. Routledge.
- [5] Robert, M. (2006). *Stress in the Work Place*. (1st Edition). New Jersey. Pearson Publishers.
- [6] Sallis, E. & Jones, G. (2002). *Knowledge Management in Education*. Great Britain: Kogan Press.
- [7] Nawaser, K., Shahmehri, F., Farhoudnia, B., & Ahmadi, M. (2015). *How Do Organizational Justice and Commitment Affect Organizational Entrepreneurship? An Empirical Investigation in Iran*. International Journal of Economics and Finance; Vol. 7, No. 2; 2015.

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

- [8] Morris, M.H., Schindehutte, M., and La Forge, R.W. (2002). *Entrepreneurial marketing: a construct for integrating emerging entrepreneurship and marketing perspectives*. Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice 10, No. 4.
- [9] Lamba, S., & Chouhary, N. (2013). *Impact of HRM Practices on Organizational Commitment of Employees*. International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology, Volume 2, Issue 4, April 2013. ISSN 2278- 7763
- [10] Ikechukwu, D. (2018). *Knowledge Management and Organizational Commitment*. International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI), vol. 07, no. 03, 2018, pp. 19–24.
- [11] Given, L. (2008). The SAGE Encyclopedia of Qualitative Research Methods. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781412963909>.
- [12] Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2013). *Research Methods in Education*. Routledge.
- [13] Nguyen, T.D., Tirthapura, S., Shih, M., Srivastava, D., & Xu, B. (2019). *Stratified random sampling from streaming and stored data*. 22nd International Conference on Extending Database Technology. ISBN 978-3-89318-081-3.
- [14] Davis, D. (2005). *Business Research for Decision Making*. Australia. Thomson South-Western.
- [15] Becherer, R.C., Helms, M.M.; and McDonald, J.P. (2012). *The Effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing on Outcome Goals in SMEs*. New England Journal of Entrepreneurship: Vol. 15 : No. 1, Article 3.
- [16] Jafri, H.(2013). *HRM Practices as Predictors of Employee Engagement: An Empirical Investigation*. Anvesha, Vol. 6 No. 4.
- [17] Jain, P. (2014). *A survey of Knowledge Management Practice among academic staff at the University of Botswana*. 25th Australasian Conference on Information Systems. 8th -10th Dec 2014, Auckland, New Zealand.
- [18] Meyer, J.P., & Allen, N.J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace: theory, research and implications*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [19] Gliem, J.A. and Gliem, R.R. (2003). *Calculating, Interpreting, and Reporting Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient for Likert-Type Scales*. Midwest Research to Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, and Community Education, Columbus, 82-88.
- [20] Okpara, J.O. (2009). *Strategic choices, export orientation and export performance of SMEs in Nigeria*. Management Decisions, 47(8), 1281-1299.
- [21] Rauch, A., Wiklund, J., Freese, M., & Lumpkin, G.T. (2004). *Entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance: Cumulative empirical evidence*. Paper presented at the 23rd Babson College Entrepreneurship Research Conference. Glasgow.
- [22] Becherer, R.C., Finch, J.H., and Helms, M.M. (2005/2006). *The Influences of Entrepreneurial Motivation and New Business Acquisition on Strategic Decision Making*, Journal of Small Business Strategy.16(2) 1-14.
- [23] Hultman, C. and Shaw, E. (2003). *The interface between transactional and relational orientation in small service firm's marketing behaviour: A study of Scottish and Swedish small firms in the service sector*. Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice 11(1), 36–51.
- [24] Marcati, A., Guido, G., and Peluso, A.Mj. (2008). *The Role of SME Entrepreneurs' Innovativeness and Personality in the Adoption of Innovations*, Research Policy, 37(9),1579–1601.
- [25] Lumpkin, G.T., & Dess, G.G. (2001). *Linking two dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation to firm performance: the moderating role of environment and life cycle*. Journal of Business Venturing, 16, 429-451.
- [26] Spence, M. and Essoussi, L.H. (2010). *SME Brand Building and Management: An Exploratory Study*. European Journal of Marketing, 44(7/8),1037–1054.
- [27] Hamali, S. (2015). *The Effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing on Business Performance : Small Garment Industry in Bandung City, Indonesia*. Developing Country Studies. ISSN 2224-607X (Paper) ISSN 2225-0565 (Online) Vol.5, No.1.

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

- [28] Hassan, S. (2016). *Impact of HRM Practices on Employee's Performance*. International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences Vol. 6, No.1, January 2016, pp. 15–22 E-ISSN: 2225-8329, P-ISSN: 2308-0337.
- [29] Kwenin, D.O., Muathe, S., and Nzulwa, R. (2013). *The Influence of Employee Rewards, Human Resource Policies and Job Satisfaction on the Retention of Employees in Vodafone Ghana Limited*. European Journal of Business and Management www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online) Vol.5, No.12.
- [30] Shoab, M., Noor, A., Tirmizi, S.R. & Bashir, S. (2009). *Determinants of Employee Retention in Telecom Sector in Pakistan*. Proceedings 2nd CBRC, Lahore, Pakistan.
- [31] Sutherland, M.M. (2004). *Factors affecting the retention of Knowledge Workers*. PhD Dissertation, Faculty of Economics and Management Sciences, University of Johannesburg.
- [32] Chong, S.C. (2005). *Implementation of Knowledge Management among Malaysian ICT Companies: An Empirical Study of Success Factors and Organizational Performance*. Malaysia Multimedia University. Unpublished.
- [33] Civi, E. (2000). *Knowledge Management as a Competitive Asset: A Review*. Marketing Intelligence and Planning. 8(4): 166-174.
- [34] Moffett, S., McAdam, R., and Parkinson, S. (2003). *An Empirical Analysis of Knowledge Management Applications*. Journal of Knowledge Management. 7(3): 6 – 26.
- [35] Theriou, N., Maditinos, D., and Therio, G. (2011). *Knowledge Management Enabler Factors and Firm Performance: An Empirical Research of the Greek Medium and Large Firms*. European Research Studies, Volume XIV, Issue (2), 2011.
- [36] Albers, J.A. (2009). *A Practical Approach to Implementing Knowledge Management*. Journal of Knowledge Management Practice (10:1). Retrieved 11 July, 2019, from <http://www.tlinc.com/articl174.htm>.
- [37] Becerra-Fernandez, I., and Sabherwal, R. (2010). *Knowledge Management: Systems and Processes*. Armonk, N.Y.: M.E. Sharpe.
- [38] Cristina, T.M. (2009). *Critical Factors to Knowledge Management Implementation*. The International Conference on Economics and Administration, Faculty of Administration and Business, University of Bucharest, Romania ICEA – FAA Bucharest, 14-15th November 2009.
- [39] Rehman, M., Mahmood, A.K.B., Sugathan, S.K., and Amin, A. (2010). *Implementation Of Knowledge Management In Small And Medium Enterprises*. Journal of Knowledge Management Practice (11:1).
- [40] Wei, C.C., and Yeganeh, M. (2013). *The Influence Of Information Technology On The Knowledge Management Process*. Journal of Knowledge Management Practice, Vol. 14, No. 1.
- [41] Khan, R., Naseem, A., & Masood, S.A. (2016). Effect of Continuance Commitment and Organizational Cynicism on Employee Satisfaction in Engineering Organizations. International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology, Vol. 7, No. 4.
- [42] Allen, N.J. and Meyer, J.P. (1990). *The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization*. Journal of Occupational Psychology, Vol. 63 No. 1, pp.1-18.
- [43] Delegach, M., Kark, R., Katz-Navon, T., & Van Dijk, D. (2017). A focus on commitment: the roles of transformational and transactional leadership and self-regulatory focus in fostering organizational and safety commitment. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 26(5), 724-740.
- [44] Nguyen, T.D., & Nguyen, V.T. (2017). *Promoting organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors in vietnamese enterprises: the influence of corporate reputation*. ICFE 2017, 365.
- [45] Kuzehchian, H., Zarei, J., Talebpour, M. (2003). *The relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction of school administrators and teachers of physical education in Khorasan province*. Journal of Olympic, Vol.32, PP:43-52.
- [46] Ghitulescu, B. (2018). *Psychosocial effects of proactivity*. Personnel Review, Vol. 47 No. 2, pp. 294-318. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-08-2016-0209>

A Causal Model on Organizational Commitment Among Cooperative Employees

- [47] Parker, S.K. & Wang, Y. (2015). *Helping people to make things happen: A framework for proactivity at work*. International Coaching Psychology Review, 10, 62-75.
- [48] Wihler, A., Blickle, G., Ellen, B.P., Hochwarter, W.A., and Ferris, G.R. (2017). *Personal initiative and job performance evaluations: Role of political skill in opportunity recognition and capitalization*. Journal of Management. 43, 1388-1420.
- [49] Olsson, M., & Matsson, J. (2015). Attitudinal commitment and business model innovation. Master's Thesis.
- [50] Hong, H., & Ha, D. (2015). *The Effects of Fast-Food Franchisor's Proactiveness, Innovation, Risk-taking on Affective Commitment, Franchisee's External Representation and Service Delivery*. Culinary science and hospitality research (한국조리학회지) Volume 21 Issue 1/Pages.191-209/2015/2466-0752(p/ISSN).
- [51] Mehwish, J., Abeera, A., Aided, B., & Tania, H. (2019). *Human resource practices and organizational commitment: The mediating role of job satisfaction in emerging economy*. Cogent Business & Management doi: 10.1080/23311975.2019.1608668.
- [52] Koc, M., Cavus, M.F., and Turgay S. (2014). *Human Resource Management Practices, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment*. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences. September 2014, Vol. 4, No. 9 ISSN: 2222-6990
- [53] Sadeghi, M. and Yazdanfar, S. (2018). *The analysis of the relationship between organizational values and commitment with regard to the knowledge management of Kermanshah's tax department staff*. Revista Lusófona de Educação, 39, 161-168.doi: 10.24140/issn.1645-7250.rle39.11
- [54] Kameli, M.J. (2009). *KM and its Obstacles in Governmental Organizations*. Journal of Karagah. Vol.2, No.3.
- [55] Ehsan, R. (2011). *Measuring the Role of Knowledge Management Processes in the Commercial Banks of Iran*. Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management, 9(4), 353-364.
- [56] Bordbar, H. (2014). *The relationship between knowledge management and organizational commitment and professional dedication of staff (Case study: oil company in south of Iran)*. M. A. Thesis, Tehran University
- [57] Sarayani, A., Mirinejad, E., & Keivani, S. (2014). *The relationship between ICT and organizational commitment among nurses*. Arth Prabhand: A Journal of Economics and Management. 3. 126-135.
- [58] Yeh, Y., & Lai, S., & Ho, C. (2006). *Knowledge Management Enablers: A Case Study*. Industrial Management and Data Systems. 106. 793-810. 10.1108/02635570610671489.
- [59] Nasiri, S. (2017). *Human Resource Management, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Performance: Development, Test and Correction of the Causal Model*. International Review of Management and Marketing, 2017, 7(3), 86-92.
- [60] Dimas B.S. & Faisal, T.I.P. (2019). *The Effect of Knowledge Management, Organizational Learning and Work Satisfaction Toward Organizational commitment and its Impact on Employee Performance in Secretariat Office, District of Nagan Raya, Aceh Province, Indonesia*. International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research. ISSN: 2455-8834 Volume: 04, Issue: 07.
- [61] Susanto, D.B. & Putra, F.T. (2019). *The Effect of Knowledge Management, Organizational Learning and Work Satisfaction Toward Organizational Commitment and its Impact on Employee Performance in Secretariat Office, District of Nagan Raya, Aceh Province, Indonesia*. International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research. Volume: 04, Issue: 07 July 2019. ISSN: 2455-8834.
- [62] Rosemond, B., Edward, M.T and Moses, A.X. (2012). *An Empirical Analysis of the Effect of Entrepreneurial orientation on firm performance of Auto Artisan in the Cope Coast Metropolis*. Developing Country Studies.